

Analysis of Compression Failures in Fibre Composite Laminates

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ABSTRACT

A three-dimensional numerical study is presented into the compressive failure of composite laminates with a delamination. Two distinct failure criteria are considered namely the strain energy density hypothesis and the energy release rate approach. In both cases the predicted far field failure strains are consistent with those measured in a number of experimental investigations and confirm that the results of specimen tests may be used for assessing the criticality of delaminations in a full scale structure.

INTRODUCTION

Although the static and residual strengths of fibre composite laminates have been examined for a number of years the bulk of the data presently available is for unflawed laminates. Furthermore the majority of studies on the strength of flawed composites have been for through the thickness slots or holes (1,2). Yet even in the case of the failure of laminates containing loaded and/or unloaded holes under compressive loading there are relatively few studies, e.g. (3,4).

As a result there has arisen a significant interest in the behaviour of damaged composites, e.g. (5,6,7). One area of particular interest is the compressive strength of laminates with either impact damage or interply delaminations (8,9,10,11). It is in this area that the present work will concentrate. The main aim is to assess the suitability of finite element analysis, coupled with a fracture mechanics approach, for determining the criticality of delaminations in coupon tests as well as in full scale structures. The fracture criteria used are the minimum strain energy density hypothesis (12) and the critical energy release rate approach. Both criteria yield results which are consistent with published experimental data.

DELAMINATION MODEL

In a recent experimental study (11) it was found that, on the compressive surface of a fibre composite structure, the effect of impact damage can be estimated from specimen tests. It was also shown that for a variety of carbon fibre laminates and ply orientations the strain at failure at a significant distance from the damage zone varied between approximately 3800×10^{-6} and

5500 X 10⁻⁶.

As a result if impact damage or interply delamination is found in a structure the criticality, and its reparability, of the damage may be assessed by either: structural component tests, or coupon tests. Since it is cheaper and often easier to perform coupon tests the present paper will attempt to model the effect of delaminations on the compressive strength of rectangular coupons. The geometry of the coupons to be examined is shown in Figure 1. The delaminations to be considered are rectangular in planform with dimensions a x w where a is the length of the delamination and w is the width of the coupon.

The laminate considered in this study is a (+45/0₂)_{2S} graphite-epoxy laminate where the basic ply is Narmco Thornel T300/5208 and the material parameters are: E₁₁ = 141 GPa, E₂₂ = E₃₃ = 9.4 GPa, G₁₂ = G₁₃ = G₂₃ = 5.0 GPa, ν₁₂ = ν₁₃ = ν₂₃ = 0.31.

Various coupon widths will be considered (viz. w = 12.7, 25.4 and 4.45 mm) and the delaminations will be considered to be at several different locations (viz. between plies 12 and 13, 13 and 14, 14 and 15, 15 and 16), see Figure 1. In each case the length of the coupon is taken as 177.8 mm.

The present finite element model follows the same general approach as used in (10,13) with each ply modelled separately and with the basic element used being the twenty noded isoparametric brick. The exceptions to this are the plies on either side of the delamination, see Figure 1. This results in a fine mesh consisting of approximately 1600 nodes. The exact number of elements and nodes being determined by the length of the delamination. Details of the grading of the mesh along any ply (i.e. the relative size of the elements) can be seen in Fig. 1(d). At the delamination front the mid-side nodes have been moved to quarter points to reproduce the required singularity. These steps were taken in order to accurately simulate the delamination and to allow for the rapid increase in the stresses along the front of the delamination.

FIG. 1 DETAILS OF COUPON GEOMETRY

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The model was loaded by compressive forces of magnitude P acting at the centre of the two ends of the coupon (see Figure 1). This form of loading was adopted to enable simple calculations to be made for the energy release rate G viz:

$$G = \frac{P}{2W} \frac{\partial \delta}{\partial a} \quad (1)$$

where δ is relative deformation at the load points in the direction of the load. In calculating G the delamination was allowed to increase in length an amount Δa . This is of course an approximate method for calculating G since the delamination will not actually grow uniformly across the width of the coupon. Nevertheless the authors feel that this yields a reasonable estimate of G . An alternative method for calculating G is by evaluating the J-integral over a closed surface around the delamination front. Then since the material is assumed to be behaving elastically we know the $G = J$.

Having calculated G then failure may be assumed to occur when $G = G_c$ where G_c is the critical energy release rate. It is particularly difficult to obtain experimental values for G_c for delamination failure. The value used in the present study is 714 N/m (=408 lb/in) which was obtained from (8) and is for a slightly different laminate namely AS3501.

In addition to the energy release rate we also calculate the minimum value of the strain energy density function S where

$$S = \frac{r}{2} \left(\sigma_{ij} \epsilon_{ij} \right)_{\min} \quad (2)$$

at $r=0$

and where $r = 0$ is the equation of the front of the delamination. In calculating S only the interlaminar and peel stresses and strains are considered and the value of S at the front (i.e. $r=0$) is interpolated from values near the front. According to this hypothesis failure will occur when

$$S = S_c \quad (3)$$

where S_c is the critical value of the matrix material. It was difficult to obtain values for S_c from the literature. The value used is 9.64 N/m (=0.55 lb/in) which was obtained from (12) for an epoxy resin similar to that used as the matrix material for T300/5208.

Let us begin by considering the case when the width $w = 12.7$ mm, the length of the delamination is 25.4 mm (i.e. $a = 25.4$ mm) and when the delamination is between the 15th and 16th plies (i.e. between the +45 and the -45 degree plies nearest the surface, see Figure 2). This results in a negative opening of the delamination along the line BB', see Figure 2, while producing a large opening of the delamination along line AA'. This phenomena is due to the asymmetric nature of the plies above and below the delamination.

Since it is physically not permissible to have a negative opening along BB' the analysis was repeated with restraints on negative opening. The results of this analysis can be seen in Table 1 along with the results for the cases when the delamination occurs between plies 12 and 13, 13 and 14, or 14 and 15. In each case the delamination was found to close along BB' and as a result the optimum value of S was found at A and A'. It is this value of S that is given in Table 1 and which is the value of the strain energy density that determines failure.

FIG. 2 DELAMINATED AREA AA'BB'

TABLE 1: Values of \sqrt{S} and \sqrt{G} for the 25.4 mm delamination, p = applied load, w = laminate width, t = laminate thickness, $E_{11} = 141$ GPa.

Delamination between	$w\sqrt{S} \frac{t E_{11}}{P}$ at point A	$w\sqrt{G} \frac{t E_{11}}{P}$
15/16	4.55×10^{-2}	0.477
14/15	4.67×10^{-2}	0.399
13/14	4.51×10^{-2}	0.420
12/13	3.11×10^{-2}	0.583

From Table 1 we see that when the delamination lies between plies 15/16, 14/15, 13/14 or 12/14 the severity of the damage, as judged by the magnitude of \sqrt{S} and \sqrt{G} , is roughly the same.

In order to investigate the effect of increasing delamination length we consider the case when the delamination lies between plies 14 and 15, i.e. between the near surface +45 and -45 degree plies. Table 2 shows the values of \sqrt{S} and \sqrt{G} for such delaminations with lengths of 12.7 mm, 25.4 mm and 38.1 mm.

TABLE 2: Values of \sqrt{S} and \sqrt{G} for various delamination lengths.

Delamination length (mm) Between plies 14 and 15	$w\sqrt{S} \frac{t E_{11}}{P}$ at A	$w\sqrt{G} \frac{t E_{11}}{P}$
12.7	3.92×10^{-2}	-
25.4	4.67×10^{-2}	0.397
38.1	5.11×10^{-2}	0.556

From this table we see that the value of the strain energy density increases as the length of the delamination increases but does not appear to be a linear function of the delamination length as in classical fracture mechanics. This is consistent with other investigations which show that failure occurs at similar strain levels for a significant range of delamination sizes. This is discussed in detail in (11) and the experimental results presented in (11) are summarized in Table 3.

Let us now examine the effect of coupon width using as an illustrative example the case when $a = 38.1$ mm and the delamination lies between plies 14 and 15. Table 4 shows the computed values of \sqrt{S} and \sqrt{G} for this configuration for widths of 12.7, 25.4 and 44.45 mm.

TABLE 3: Compressive strength of various impact damaged laminates. From reference (11).

	SKIN THICKNESS MM	DELAMINATION AREA MM ²	COMPRESSIVE FAILURE STRAIN X10 ⁻⁶
AS/3501-6 (±45/0 ₂ /±45/0 ₂ /±45/0/90) _{2S}	6.91	1290	3780
AS/3501-6 (±45/90/-45/+22.5/-67.5/-22.5/±67.5/ ±45/+67.5/+22.5/-67.5/-22.5/±67.5/ ±22.5/0 ₂ /±22.5) _S	6.45	1629	4630
AS/3501-6 (0/±45/0 ₂ /±45/0) SKIN ON HRP-3/16-5.5 HONEYCOMB CORE	1.07	1161	4270
AS/3501-6 (±45/0*/±45/0 ₂ */90*/0 ₂ */±45*/0 ₂ */±45*/ 0*/±45*/0*/±45*/0*/-45*/0*/±45*) _S	12.7	2839	4090
AS/3501-6 (90*/-45*/±67.5/±22.5*/0/90*/±22.5*/ 0 ₂ /±45*/0*/-22.5*/±45*/±67.5*/±22.5*/ -67.5*/-45*/±22.5*/0) _S	11.10	7097	5460
TF300/5208 (±45/0 ₂ /±45/0 ₂ /±45/0/90) _S	6.71	1419	4000
T300/5208 (±45/0/90/±45/0/90) _{3S}	6.71	1226	4000
(±45/0/±45/0/±45/0) _S GRAPHITE SKIN ON 1/8 IN - 5.5 HONEYCOMB CORE	2.29	1290	4000

* DOUBLE-PLY MATERIAL, ALL OTHERS SINGLE PLY.

TABLE 4: Variation of \sqrt{S} and \sqrt{G} with width

width mm.	$w\sqrt{S} \text{ t } E_{11}/P$	$w\sqrt{G} \text{ t } E_{11}/P$	delamination area mm ²
12.7	5.11×10^{-2}	0.556	483
25.4	6.26×10^{-2}	0.631	967
44.45	7.91×10^{-2}	0.738	1694

This shows that S and G are dependent on the width of the delamination with an increase in width resulting in an increase in S and G. Indeed this again illustrates that a two-dimensional analysis of the present problem is not applicable.

On the basis of the results given in Table 4 it is possible to predict the far field strain at failure. For example in the case when the delaminated area is 1694 mm² we find that $S = (.0791 P/w)^2/t E_{11}$ and $G = (0.738 P/w)^2/t E_{11}$.

Taking $G = G_c$ as the failure criteria for delamination growth and the value of G_c to be 714 N/m (= 4.08 lb/in), obtained from reference (8), yields a far field failure strain of approximately 3800×10^{-6} . Alternatively if we take $S = S_c$ as the failure criteria for delamination growth and use $S_c = 9.64$ N/m (= 0.055 lb/in), obtained from (12), we obtain a far field failure strain of approximately 4300×10^{-6} .

This size delamination lies in the range of delaminations given in Table 3 and the failure strain predicted using either criteria also lie within the experimentally observed failure strains.

At this point it is important to note that failure of the delamination may not necessarily coincide with the final failure of the structure although this was the case in the wing box test reported in (11). In practice delamination failure results in an asymmetric laminate and final failure of the laminate is due to the resultant increase in the net section stresses and out of plane bending due to asymmetry. As a result the load required to cause failure of the delamination represents a lower bound on the load to cause final failure of the structure.

It should also be stressed that the values of G_c and S_c used above may not be the exact values for this laminate. Hence if these procedures are to be used in assessing flaw criticality then accurate experimental values of G_c and S_c need to be obtained for a variety of laminates. In addition tests need to be undertaken to determine the failure loads of asymmetric laminates.

CONCLUSION

We have seen that the presence of delaminations results in asymmetric laminates above and below the disbond. This asymmetry results in out of plane bending and twisting under in plane compressive loading. It is this bending and twisting which results in delamination crack growth. Indeed it has shown that the strain energy density and the energy release rate methods are capable of predicting failure of the delamination. If these methods are to be widely used for predicting critical flaw sizes it is necessary to undertake a series of experimental tests to determine S_c and G_c and the load at final failure.

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